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ADVANCEMENT OF THE INDUSTRIAL ROBOT PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE L-IRL USING AUGMENTED REALITY

Abstract: *Augmented reality is one of the most promising technologies in the development of a new generation of human-machine interfaces. In this paper, the advancement of Lola Industrial Robot programming language (L-IRL) using Augmented Reality is presented. A developed tool for programming linear path segments of Tool Centre Point (TCP) in an AR environment representing an upgraded online Walk-Through robot programming method is described. Development has been performed in Unity IDE. A path planner adapted for variable and unpredictable Unity frame rates has been used. A post-processor for generating L-IRL code has been presented. Verification is performed for the 6DoF industrial robot with revolutes joints RL-15.*

Key words: *industrial robot, offline robot programming, augmented reality.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Industrial robots are important equipment for automatization in the modern manufacturing industry, integrating advanced multi-disciplinary technology, such as machinery, electronics, control, computers, sensors, artificial intelligence, etc [1]. A robot application program is a set of instructions that cause the robot system to move the robot's end-effector, i.e. Tool Center Point (TCP) in order to perform the desired robot task correctly [2]. Conventional industrial robot programming methods are time-consuming, and often require specialized expertise [3]. Over the years, tremendous efforts have been undertaken by the international robotics community to achieve user-friendly and, at the same time, powerful programming methods [4-5].

Recently, Augmented Reality (AR) has been used to advance the programming process of industrial robots [4-6]. Augmented Reality is used to enhance the perception of the real world by integrating virtual objects into an image sequence acquired from various camera technologies [7]. Numerous AR applications in robotics in industrial settings have been developed in recent years [7-8].

In this paper, the advancement of Lola Industrial Robot programming language (L-IRL) [9-10] using Augmented Reality technology is presented. A developed tool for programming of linear path segments of Tool Centre Point (TCP) in an AR environment which can be regarded as an upgraded online Walk-Through robot programming method [4] is described.

The paper is divided as follows. In section 2, system specifications and requirements have been presented. Integration methodology has been given in Section 3. Verification of the proposed AR-supported robot programming tool is presented in Section 4. Discussion and concluding remarks are given in sections 5 and 6.

2. SYSTEM SPECIFICATIONS AND REQUIREMENTS

2.1 L-IRL language

A series of LOLA robot controllers, were developed and are being constantly upgraded in Lola Institute [11]. A new system for robot control, programming, and remote monitoring is software-oriented, open architecture, modular, and reconfigurable [11-12].

L-IRL is a procedural robot programming language that belongs to the class of higher programming languages and is developed at the Lola Institute according to the standard DIN 66312 - Industrial Robot Language (IRL), for the purposes of programming industrial robots [9-11]. An integral part of the L-IRL trajectory planner is the trajectory interpolator, whose outputs are the positions, velocities, and accelerations of the manipulator's joints, which are sent to the servo controllers at discrete time intervals, which are constant [9]. Programs written in the L-IRL language are compiled and then executed on the real-time robot controller [13], Fig. 1. L-IRL contains all general structures such as data processing, expressions, program flow control, procedures and operations, as well as robot specific structures, geometric data types, and expressions, motion statements, etc.

Fig. 1. Information flow in robot control system [9]

The motion instructions (so-called MOVE instructions) within the L-IRL language allow standard movements in industrial robotics, such as Point to Point (PTP) motions or Continuous Path (CP) movements of the robot's end-effector. In CP motion [12], a user defines a path to be followed by a TCP, such as linear, circle, etc. MOVE instructions are implemented through functions and procedures within the trajectory planner.

2.2 AR-supported upgraded Walk-Through robot programming tool

Industrial robot programming is usually performed using offline or online programming methods [2]. Conventional online programming methods, such as the Lead-Through method [4], i.e., robot programming using teaching pendant, is time-consuming, require downtime, and often require specialized expertise. Offline programming methods require high-fidelity 3D modeling of the robot and its workspace and are time-consuming [3]. The Walk-Through robot programming method [4] is an intuitive programming method where the human operator interacts directly with the robot by physically guiding it to the desired configuration. However, this method has two shortcomings. The first one is that it is an online method, which implies downtime, and the second one is that it is limited, as only a few lightweight robots offer the necessary zero-torque control [4].

In this research, we propose an upgraded AR-supported Walk-Through robot programming method, where offline programming of linear segments of TCP paths is enabled in an Augmented Reality environment in an online mode, and integrated with online Walk-Through programming for the definition of starting and ending TCP poses for linear path segments of a TCP.

3. INTEGRATION PROCESS

3.1 System integration

Unity [14], one of the most popular game engines, is a leading platform for the development of XR applications with high-quality 3D rendering, which can be deployed across a variety of platforms and can integrate different XR SDKs. In this study, Unity has been used as IDE. Coding is done in C#. In marker-based AR, scanning a marker triggers an augmented experience. In this paper, a smartphone/tablet was chosen as a tool for experiencing Augmented Reality. Vuforia [15], an AR Software Development Kit for mobile devices that provides essential tools for the creation of Augmented Reality applications, is used for generating AR robot image in a real laboratory environment

Development in Unity includes the following [16]:

- Development of a robot model for robot's motion simulation in Unity, based on the robot's CAD model, utilizing Unity's built-in physics engine, Nvidia PhysX, and setting up motion controllers [17]. The complete procedure is described in [16].
- Development of AR-supported upgraded offline Walk-Through robot programming functionality, including:
 - integration of solution of inverse kinematics

problem;

- integration of trajectory planner;
 - developing of functionalities for robot programming in AR;
 - development of GUI, including touchscreen interaction.
- Development of L-IRL post-processor.

In Fig. 2, a render of the 6DoF robot RL15 in the laboratory environment based on the developed 3D robot model is presented. The system architecture for the proposed AR-supported robot programming framework is presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Render of the 6DoF robot RL15 in the laboratory environment

Fig. 3. System architecture for the designed AR-supported robot programming system

3.2 Trajectory planner development

Given that a standalone application has been considered herein, a trajectory planner had to be integrated. In this research, for the purposes of system verification, a separated simple trajectory planner enabling the programming of CP motion along linear paths in Unity has been used, previously developed in [16]. The planner integrates the solution for the inverse kinematics problem for the specific robot, in this case RL15, which was previously developed and presented in [9]. The planner operates by calculating the current poses using normalized time and coordinates, integrating inverse kinematics (IK) algorithms for real-time execution, and checking joint positions and speeds against predefined limits. Given that the Unity frame rate is variable and not predictable, in this research, a trajectory planner calculates joint positions for the current frame using analytical expressions and Unity built-in functions for time measurement in real-time systems. The trajectory generation relies on a cubic polynomial to smooth the path between selected poses [16]. The real-time calculation ensures that joint positions and speeds are continuously monitored and

remain within predefined limits, thereby maintaining the accuracy and safety of the robot's movements.

4. VERIFICATION OF THE NOVEL L-IRL AR-SUPPORTED TOOL FOR OFFLINE UPGRADED WALK-THROUGH PROGRAMMING OF LINEAR TCP MOTIONS

Verification of the novel L-IRL AR-supported tool for offline upgraded Walk-Through programming in an AR environment is performed using 6DoF robot RL15 previously produced in Lola Institute [9]. Fig. 4 depicts the developed GUI for the designed AR-supported Android robot programming app, with the designed various buttons and a vertical stack of numerical values of the real-time TCP position and orientation of the augmented robot in Cartesian space, and the joint angles of augmented robot.

Fig. 4. Depiction of GUI for AR-supported robot programming system in the laboratory settings. [15]

Fig. 5 shows the programming of robot RL15 using the designed Android smartphone application. Scanning a marker triggers an augmented experience, i.e. loading and initialization of the robot's RL15 3D model in Augmented Reality. The augmented robot is scaled down for demonstration purposes.

Fig. 5. GUI for AR-supported advanced Walk-Through robot programming

Advanced AR-supported Walk-through robot programming allows the user to select start and end points between linear paths of the robot's TCP in a very simple way. A user manually “drags” the TCP frame in an AR environment by using a phone as an emulated robot handle. In other words, the robot's TCP frame

follows the movement of the user's hand holding the smartphone until the user decides to select and save a point in Cartesian space that marks the position of the TCP, while the orientation is defined by the orientation of the phone. This is achieved by the TCP coordinate frame becoming a child of the AR camera frame.

When the user selects several poses of the TCP in the Cartesian space, which is done by a user pressing the button as presented in Fig 5., they can simulate the programmed trajectory of the robot in Augmented Reality, which herein implies a linear TCP path between the selected waypoints. The TCP linear trajectory is achieved by robot joint motions calculated by the trajectory planner.

A user can inspect the programmed trajectory from multiple angles during different time instances/robot configurations using the slider. This is depicted in Fig.6.

Fig. 6. Simulation of the programmed movements in AR

If the user is satisfied with the programmed trajectory, they can decide to save it. The TCP poses are then sent to the developed post-processor for L-IRL language, and saved to a .txt file as L-IRL code, Fig. 7.

```

file:///mnt/.../View
program lol15_00;
const
  real:locIntr:=center.yourValue;
  real:locZable:=center.yourValue;
  real:locIntr:=center.yourValue;
  real:locZable:=center.yourValue;
  (point:pe:= locIntr(locIntr(0,0,0,0,0)));
endconst
seq
mov0 100 posttarget(pos(position(178.3240,278.6868,61.16818), orientation(145.7085,277.5228,66.51118))) speed=writeIntr acc=writeIntr e_get=to_val act_robot="100000";
mov0 100 posttarget(pos(position(41.45472,287.2216,68.31685), orientation(148.841,269.4026,66.58847))) speed=writeIntr acc=writeIntr e_get=to_val act_robot="100000";
mov0 100 posttarget(pos(position(189.1767,278.5875,58.31685), orientation(148.413,279.4018,65.46653))) speed=writeIntr acc=writeIntr e_get=to_val act_robot="100000";
endseq
endprogram.

```

Fig. 7. L-IRL code generated by developed post-processor

5. DISCUSSION

The presented AR-supported CP robot programming tool represents the integration of conventional Walk-Through online programming method with offline continuous-path programming, leveraging advantages of both methods, namely the absence of downtime for offline programming, and the intuitive programming approach characteristic for the Walk-Through online programming method.

In robot programming, AR and, in general, XR technologies are primarily utilized to enhance visualization which benefits the robot programming

process. XR (Extended Reality) offers substantial benefits by immersing programmers in a virtual environment where they can intuitively visualize the robot's end-effector (TCP) movements within the real world. This immersion aids in identifying and understanding the robot's operational constraints in its real-world view.

Presented AR-supported industrial robot CP programming tool can be standalone, as presented in [16], or it can be created using integration of Unity with ROS [18] (ROS–Unity suite), offline/online programming environments like RoboDK [19] and other similar robot frameworks. Advantages and disadvantages are presented in [16].

6. FINAL REMARKS

In this paper, the improvement of the Lola Industrial Robot programming language using Augmented Reality technology is presented. A software tool for intuitive programming of continuous paths (linear path segments of TCP) in offline mode using Augmented Reality technology is presented. Development has been performed in Unity IDE. A post-processor for generating L-IRL code has been developed. Verification is performed for 6DoF industrial robot RL-15.

7. REFERENCES

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